

Understanding the Need for Gender-Sensitive Green Spaces in Urban Areas

Ar. Charu Arora Mathur¹ and Dr. Rashmi Asht²

Ar. Charu Arora Mathur: Research Scholar, Doctorate of Philosophy, Department of Architecture and Planning, Indira Gandhi Delhi Technical University for Women, Kashmere Gate, Delhi, India.

Prof. (Dr.) Rashmi Asht: Professor, Department of Architecture and Planning, Indira Gandhi Delhi Technical University for Women, Kashmere Gate, Delhi, India.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Urban green areas are the spaces in city fabric which are partly or fully covered with vegetation (Environmental Protection Agency, n.d., <https://www3.epa.gov/region1/eco/uep/openspace.html>). These spaces include parks, gardens, playgrounds, zoological parks and urban forestry. Green spaces are required in the city to sustain urban environmental quality and social well-being of city dwellers (Ridder, Adamecb, et al. 2004). The green areas in urban settings offer space for recreational, physical and social activities to the people in living in cities and thereby help in improving citizen's habitable experiences (Sangwan et al., 2022).

Traditionally the landscape design of urban green spaces (UGS) has been done keeping in mind the variables like climate, culture and regional influence. Urban green space design has received a lot of attention in recent decades in an effort to balance and alleviate environmental problems brought on by rapid urban growth. To design an ecologically sound landscape, numerous environmentally sustainable factors are taken into consideration. The social factors (the role of gender) and their influence on the design of green spaces have lost their association in order to achieve these goals.

The 2030 Agenda, adopted by all United Nations Member in 2015, aims for a gender-responsive and inclusive design in cities. Three of these Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) contribute toward achieving these targets: SDG 5 on “*achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls*”; SDG 11 on “*making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable*”; and SDG 16 on “*promoting peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development* (United Nations, n.d., <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>).” The emphasis on gender equality and women's empowerment has been acknowledged as a foundation policy for addressing the key international development goals. The United Nations Human Settlement programme encourages spatial planning and design as a way to reunite and incorporate spatial, social, economic, cultural and environmental issues in a community (UN-Habitat, 2012).

Women face many challenges in the urban green areas: personal safety, accessibility, vulnerability, hurdles to take part in local decision making processes, accessing data that might impact their equal right to opportunities and resources, etc. (Paul & Nagendra, 2017; Polko & Kimic, 2022). There have been earlier studies which suggest that women have

different sensitivities and expectations from green spaces and they perceive urban green spaces differently from men (Polko & Kimic, 2022; Olta, Marco, & José, 2021).

For an inclusive design it is essential to address requirements from the green space by all the users of a community. It is essential to identify facilitators and barriers related to use of green spaces by both men and women. To achieve a socially comprehensive urban green space it is important to make sure that programs, strategies and projects positively impact and strengthen gender equivalence as part of the development practices.

According to World Economic Forum 2022, “Global Gender Gap report”, India ranks 135 out of 146 countries. The ranking is based on four indexes – Economic participation and opportunity; Education attainment; health and survival and; political empowerment. It lacks to address the impact of physical planning of green space on genders.

There is a further need to understand the concept, functionality, and psychological impact the green spaces have on their users (Sangwan et al., 2022). The objectives of this research are: (i) to highlight the gap in urban green space planning and lack of gender sensitive design criteria and physical planning guidelines in India; (ii) to understand the issues of various genders in using UGS (like perception of safety in green spaces, etc.) (iii) to know what are activity requirements by different genders inside the park premises; and (iv) to finally suggest the parameters of gender sensitization and its importance in planning UGS by the Planners and designers to develop new paradigm and strategies with gender inclusion in urban planning framework.

1.1 *Gender issues associated with use and experience of UGS*

Historically the urban parks have evolved as places to stimulate nature, play areas for children, area to offer recreational services, at times as centres to generate revenue (Cranz, 2005). Over the years the green spaces in cities have been used for recreation and leisure. Planners have identified its economic, cultural, environmental, and social values. The designers, planners and policy makers have traditionally demarcated urban green spaces as areas for maintaining ecological balance, climatic and physical benefits, to improve aesthetic image of cities, for improving health benefits (mental and physical) for its citizens and increasing revenues from tourism.

Over the decades, the green urban spaces have been developed for environmental and economic benefits. This has led to overlooking human needs from these green open spaces. These green spaces are used by both men and women, but the experience of both the genders may be different. There various issues that women and other gender minorities face in using these green areas are –

Accessibility - There are studies going on in India and other parts of the world, which suggest the relationship between user accessibility and frequency and optimal use of green spaces (Gupta, Luthra, et al., 2016). The cities have two types of spaces – public and private. Public spaces include - streets, plazas, squares and parks that are open and accessible for all (Yasemin, 2014). Private spaces are areas which are privately owned by individuals.

Traditionally women have been associated with private spaces as their “primary role” is of “care taker and reproduction”. While men “go out for work and earn for family”, so the public spaces have been designed keeping their requirements in mind. The zoning of the cities reflects this segregation in planning of public and private spaces (The World Bank, 2020).

This leads to women often facing barriers in accessing urban green areas as it creates additional burden of travelling longer distances. This travelling takes a lot of time and energy and creates discomfort for women.

Mobility – Distance is the main factor for accessing and using urban green areas. Women generally walk shorter distances to these green spaces (Mayen & Utomo, 2022). A city has various hierarchies of green spaces; all may not be within walking distance. At times, women and other gender minorities have to rely on public transportation to access these green areas.

The transportation planning in city is done keeping in mind the men’s travelling routes to their workplaces. Women often travel combining various stops for multiple tasks. There is not much flexibility in public transit system for this variability (The World Bank, 2020; Mayen & Utomo, 2022). Another issue in mobility is the time. Women avoid going out in the dark due to safety concerns.

Safety – Cities have a very high crime rate. Safety is a major concern for accessing and using green spaces (Pablo et al., 2021). “*Men and women perceive and value the characteristics of urban green spaces differently, as both have different sensitivities and expectations* (Olta, Marco, & José, 2021).” There are various factors which characterize the safety perception of green spaces - lighting, cleanliness, maintenance, shaded areas, vegetation, seating, views, recreational areas etc. (Olta, Marco, & José, 2021; Yasemin, 2014; Mayen & Utomo, 2022; Pablo et al., 2021). The fear of crime restricts the mobility and access of women and gender minorities within the green spaces (The World Bank, 2020).

Health – Green urban spaces have been associated with health benefits for people. Studies have been done to understand the effect of green areas on the health of different genders (Richardson & Mitchell, 2010). These studies suggest that the health benefits are not uniform for all genders. This is because both the genders perceive and use the green spaces in different manner (Paul & Nagendra, 2017; Polko & Kimic, 2022; Richardson & Mitchell, 2010).

Use of green space – people use green spaces in cities for recreation purpose, socializing, to improve mental and physical well-being (Phillips et al., 2022). For the benefit of men and women, the urban green spaces should be designed for “*recreational pursuits and participation of both the genders*” (Natu, 2008). The activity mapping and observations can help designers to spatially articulate the spaces for the use by males and females.

The figure one below summarizes the gender issues associated with Urban Green spaces that need to be addressed by city planners and designers.

Fig.1: Gender Issues Associated with UGS
Source: Author

There are other issues which influence the use of green spaces in urban settings, e.g. family income, fitness level, physical disabilities, job, education, cultural background etc. (Sanga et al., 2020). For a more equal and positive usage of urban green spaces, the planning and developmental strategies need to take gender difference into account.

1.2 Urban green spaces in India

India has a diverse classification and hierarchy of green areas (Sangwan et al., 2022). The environmental movement in 1960s led to integration of green spaces into urban fabric of the cities (Hindustan Times, n.d.). The green spaces were developed for ecological benefit, socio-cultural and health benefits of people living in cities.

The green spaces in India include – Forests, national parks, agricultural land, grasslands, green belts, sports activity areas, parks and gardens. In India, different cities have developed their own categorization, classification and hierarchies of green space (Sangwan et al., 2022). The planning authorities have defined different hierarchies of urban green spaces. The figure two below shows the various green space categories and their hierarchies as defined by Urban and regional development plans formulation and implementation guidelines (2014).

Figure 2: Typology of green spaces in India

The green spaces have been categorized in various hierarchies according to use of the green spaces and the accessibility to the users. The current hierarchies define the general activities and functions of these green areas, for example, tot lots are meant as play areas, city level parks are meant as family recreation spaces on weekends, etc. The generalization of these “functions” does not take into account the gender needs (activities, uses, perception etc.) from these green built environments. The lack of sensitivity towards gender sensitive design approach will make the green space not perform its “function” in the city. For a more sustainable use of these urban green spaces at different levels it is important to understand physical and psychological requirements, perceptions and impacts these hierarchies of green spaces have on genders.

WHO (world Health Organization) prescribes 9sq.m green space per capita for cities and it also recommends that green spaces in a city should be planned within fifteen minutes of walking distance from residential areas (Citizen Matters, n.d). In India, Urban Development ministry made guidelines in 1996 for metropolitan cities to develop 20-25% of total developed area as recreational areas, comprising of – parks, playgrounds, botanical gardens, and open spaces (Citizen Matters, n.d). The Urban and regional development plans formulation and implementation (URDPFI) guidelines were formulated in 2014 and there it was recommended to incorporate this in master plans of Indian cities. In India there is a lack of monitoring system to track whether these guidelines are followed or up to which level they are incorporated in master plans. The data from Urban Greening guidelines of 2014 highlights the gaps in per capita green space in Indian cities and global peer cities. It also identifies the absence of information about the quantity and quality of urban green spaces.

To understand the gaps in recommendations and implementation of urban green guidelines and quality of green spaces designed for various city users, Delhi, India has been taken as the study area.

2.0 STUDY AREA

The study is focussed on Delhi, the capital of India. According to 2011 census, Delhi and National Capital Territory (NCT) of Delhi is the largest metropolitan area in India and has an estimated population of 28 million. It is one of the greenest capitals in the world with 20% forest cover (Hindustan Times, n.d.). This is due to the forest departments’ emphasis on greening and strict rules for tree cutting (Hindustan Times, n.d.; Sangwan et al., 2022). The green cover in Delhi has seen substantial growth, particularly between 2001 and 2017, when it nearly doubled. This increase can largely be attributed to initiatives by the forest department and various greening agencies. As of 2021, Delhi's total green cover, including forests, tree cover, and plantations, had risen by over 5% compared to previous decades, reaching 23.06% of the city's geographical area. The graph in figure three, which shows the doubling of green cover in Delhi from 2001 to 2017, is a clear reflection of these sustained efforts (Delhi Forest Department).

Fig. 3 Green-cover in Delhi
Source: Author

Delhi has a mix of natural and planned green areas. The ridge area has been categorized as Regional Park in master plan. Delhi has more than 18,000 parks and gardens. The green spaces in Delhi are unevenly scattered. The densely populated areas have lowest per capita green in India (MPD-2041). This makes for an unbalanced access to green areas in the city.

The first Master Plan of Delhi was made for the period of 1961-81. In this plan, Delhi Development Authority (DDA) allocated spaces for local, district and regional parks. The agricultural belt was proposed on city's periphery. The second master plan was proposed for the period of 1981-2001. In this plan the focus was on conservation of Delhi's natural green habitat – Aravalli Ridge and River Yamuna. The third master plan was proposed for a period of 2001-2021. It emphasised on improving Delhi's environment – water and air pollution due to rapid urbanization (Rumi, 2021). It was also planned to align the zonal plans with master plan to provide major access roads to various green development areas in the city.

Some studies like – “spatial distribution of green areas, area under surface water bodies, air and water quality, noise levels, drainage, sanitation, and local temperatures” (Rumi, 2021) have been done by various agencies to improve Delhi's environment. These have been incorporated in Proposed 2041 Delhi Master Plan.

Draft Master Plan of Delhi (MPD) - 2041 is an intended comprehensive plan for development of Delhi up to the year 2041. The focus of 2041 master plan is to improve Delhi's environmental conditions by providing various planning proposals. According to the draft MPD 2041, “the city is quite green but these greens are inequitably distributed. The quality of greens also needs to be improved at many places”. It also states that, “a hierarchy of parks, greens and open spaces for meeting different types and scales of needs shall be implemented in greenfield, as well as brownfield areas” (MPD-2041). Urban green spaces in Delhi have been categorized into various hierarchies according to - population, number of parks, area standards, use premise, FAR, minimum plot area and maximum ground coverage. Tot lots at local level are the lowest in the hierarchy, followed by community level parks, sub-city level parks and City level parks (Table 2). The various types of green spaces are –

Local Level	Community Level	Subcity Level	City Level
Tot Lot	Community Park	District Park	Regional Park
Housing area Park	Community Multipurpose ground	District Multipurpose Ground	City Park
Housing area playground	Community sports Centre	District Sports Centre	City Multipurpose Ground
Local level Park			Theme Based/ Amusement Parks
Local Level Play area			Archaeological Parks
			Biodiversity Parks
			Green Buffer
			City Level sports: Divisional Sports Centre

Table 1: Hierarchy of green spaces defined in draft MPD 2041

Source: Author

The green areas of the city have been categorized into various hierarchies (according to use) with defined activities (MPD-2041). The typological classification of Green assets in Delhi as per draft MPD 2041 is given in table two below.

Natural and existing	Recreational areas	Green assets within built fabric	New and potential City level Green
Aravalli (Ridge), Regional Parks, Reserved Forest	Planned parks and open spaces of all hierarchies – regional, city, district, community, neighbourhood, housing area, tot lots, multipurpose grounds, golf courses, and playgrounds.	Private gardens, courtyards, rooftop gardens, pools, internal streets etc.	Abandoned mines and quarries, power plants and land fill sites/ reclaimed land.
Protected Forests	Sports centres/ complexes, golf courses	Large green areas identified in Institutional/ Government campuses	Newly developed Buffers of natural drains
City Forests	Orchards, plant nurseries	Surface/open parking areas, public plazas	Green Development Area
Biodiversity Parks	Zoological park and botanical gardens	Mandatory green areas in closed industrial estates, LBZ, buffers of HT lines/oil pipelines/ other services	
Buffers of natural drains and water bodies		Residual space under flyovers, along water mains, along railway lines, etc.	
Archaeological Parks and Greens of historical monuments		Herbs, spice gardens, greenhouses.	
Areas for natural protection/conservation identified by government agencies		Plantation on central verge of roads, tree cover along roads and streets	

Table 2: Typology of green spaces, as defined in draft MPD 2041

Source: Author

The draft MPD 2041 has the policies for green belt development areas, environment, economy, mobility, heritage, culture and public spaces (Times of India, 2021). For the urban green spaces, the draft suggests hierarchies and typologies of green spaces for improving and increasing the green cover of Delhi, minimizing pollution and climate change and increasing green mobility. Norms for walkability, transit-oriented development, unauthorised colonies, etc. have also been introduced to improve upon liveability in Delhi.

The aim of draft MPD 2041 is to focus on “*facilitating more women to join the workforce by providing safe and gender-friendly streets, public spaces and workplaces with adequate childcare facilities*” (MPD-2041). The draft does not define any safety standards or policies for women, children, transgender, elderly and other vulnerable sections in public and open spaces of Delhi. To create a more inclusive and equitable city for all its citizens, it is important to understand the needs and fears of all genders and sections of society, so that these issues can be addressed in planning process.

2.1. Sample area selection

The District Park, Sector 14, Rohini, Delhi was selected to know the requirements and safety perception of Urban Green Areas by different genders. It is also known as Chitragupt park, covers an area of thirty acres and is located behind Rohini East metro station in sector 14, Rohini. The park is maintained by Delhi Development Authority (DDA). The entry to the park is free and it is open all 365 days of the year from 4:30am to 9:00pm.

The park was chosen as a study area because it serves as a major green space in densely populated area of Delhi. Rohini is a home to diverse population, which means the park attracts a variety of users – the diversity makes the park a suitable place to study the needs and concerns of different user groups. It is also easily accessible to diverse users and has continuous flow of users throughout the day. This creates an environment to observe patterns of park usage, peak visiting time and difference in how safety concerns are perceived differently by different user groups.

The park is well located with residential plots on one side and apartment complexes on other and hostels for students studying at institutions around the park. The park is divided in various zones – the periphery of the park has dense vegetation with soft walking trail, parking on two sides for park users, central park with fountain and green areas for walking and spending quiet time in the park, Gym and playground and children playing equipments are together, community green areas with badminton facility are located separately and woodlands are maintained near sports complex area.

Fig. 4: Selected Park (District Park, Sec-14, Rohini) in Delhi

Fig. 5: Pictures inside the District Park premises

(A) Washroom – unsafe, surrounded by dense vegetation.

(B) Pergola in Central park – well maintained, inviting for both genders.

(C) Entry to Central park – handicap accessible, paved paths.

- (D) Back of Metro Station - unsafe, surrounded by unmaintained vegetation and litter.
- (E) Children Play area - lots of options for children, no seating facility for parents / caretakers. Next to active football / cricket play areas. Kids/ caretakers sometimes get hurt by the ball.
- (F) Gym Area – mostly occupied by kids for playing with gym equipments. Rest of the times it is used by males who access park for exercise and physical activities.
- (G) Woodland area – women feel insecure in this space as visibility is limited due to obstructed sightlines, and dense vegetation, which contribute to increase perceptions of vulnerability.
- (H) Compost pit – unsightly and a space for security concern.
- (I) Trail along periphery – mostly accessed by men for jogging.

3.0 Methodology

The purpose of this paper is to understand the needs of various genders in terms of use and perception of urban green areas. The research also tries to highlight the gaps in planning and designing green space in a city without considering gender as an important variable.

Extensive literature studies about the issues associated with the use and experience of different genders in urban green spaces has been done. To understand the extent of gender inclusion in physical planning in India, the studies of guidelines made by Urban Development ministry 1996, Urban and regional development plans formulation and implementation guidelines (2014) and how they are incorporated in master plans of various cities have been done.

The study is focussed on Delhi, India. To understand the situation in Delhi, the studies of previous and proposed master plans of Delhi, regional has been done in detail. Also, a live case study of a District Park in in Rohini sector-14, Delhi has been done.

Before the design and conduct of the survey, observational studies were done to understand the zoning of the park and how the various activities have been planned in the park for its users. A survey of total 80 park visitors was conducted. The survey was conducted both in online and offline mode. Approximate time to completely fill the survey form was 8-10 minutes. The surveys were done on both weekends and weekdays in morning, afternoon and evening times on different days. The visitors were randomly approached and some of them were also interviewed while they were filling the survey.

Some park users were vary of filling the survey or giving their names or contact information but did fill the survey after the intent for survey was explained to them. 4-5 people just walked away as we approached them with the survey forms in the park. To get more responses of people who lived closer to the district park, Presidents of Resident welfare

association (RWA) of plotted houses and of one the housing societies next to the park were approached to float an online survey on their whatsapp groups. Below is the sample of survey form which was floated to collect data.

Through the survey, the data was collected on i) demographics – Name, age, gender, education qualification; ii) distance, mode and frequency of visiting the park; iii) purpose of visiting the park, space preferences inside the park premises; iv) additional activities required and; v) safety and security issues, concerns and improvement required in the park premises.

4. Results

The survey was done in months from Oct-Dec 2022. In total 37 survey forms were filled inside the park premises, 43 online responses were recorded and Approximately 8-10 interviews were conducted to understand more in detail about the perception of safety and activity requirements in this park by various genders.

4.1 Demographics of respondents

Out of the 80 surveyed visitors, 46 were women and 34 were men. No respondent specified any other gender. The visitors were grouped in age group of - 18 to 29, 30 to 44, 45 to 59 and 60+ years. With respect to the data, women in age groups of 18-29 and 30-44 dominated the user group. Whereas men in age groups of 30-44 and 60+ dominated the user group. The children were not surveyed separately as they were always accompanied by adults. The education qualification of the sample surveyed was almost similar for both men and women (65% women with higher education and 71% men with higher education, Fig.6). The uneducated women visitors were mostly the house helpers who worked nearby and were taking a lunch break in the park. There were some uneducated men too in the park, but they were reluctant to be the part of the survey.

Fig 6: Demographic Data of the respondents

4.2 Distance, mode and frequency of visiting the park

With respect to the socio demographic data, more number of women residing in closer vicinity to the park accessed the park by walking. As the residential distance increased from the park, the number of women users accessing the park decreased. The occasional visitors were mostly the students studying in institutes nearby, they travelled via the metro. Frequency of visiting the park every alternate day is more for men. Most of the surveyed women were not the regular park visitors; they accessed the park monthly or occasionally.

Fig. 7: Socio demographic data of park users

4.3 Purpose of visit to the park

According to the data collected through the survey, women preferred to be in open meadow like green spaces (the green central space of the park is highly maintained and aesthetically designed), children play areas and open gym areas in the park. Men preferred to be on the

running tracks, which has physical exercise equipment strewn along it and paved areas around the fountains.

Nearly 50% of both men and women go to the park for walking. According to the survey, the additional reasons given for visiting the park by women are that they go there to accompany their kids to the play areas, socialise with their peer groups, and get some fresh air. Whereas, most of the men respondents cited - exercise, jogging and other kind of physical activities as the main purpose of their visit to the park.

Fig.8 : (A) Spaces preferred in Park

(B) Purpose of visit to the park

4.4 Additional Activities

When asked about any additional activities they would prefer in the park – around 30% of both men and women felt no need of additional activities. They also stressed on additional requirement of equipments for people with special needs. More than 30% women also responded that allocation of community gardening space would be preferable, while men wanted a food Kiosk in the park.

Fig.9: Additional activities preferred by different genders in the Park

4.5 Safety and Security

From the safety perspective more than 80% of the respondents (both men and women) felt quiet safe in the park premises. More than 50% women respondents identified the central green area of the park to the safest zone. Apart from these spaces, men stated the trail along the periphery with dense vegetation around it, to be quiet safe too. Back areas of the metro station, densely vegetated areas near compost pit, washrooms, and vegetated areas near boundary were highlighted as unsafe areas of the park by both the genders. Women also highlighted the washrooms to be unsafe as they were surrounded by dense vegetation.

Lack of CCTV's and users who drink alcohol and played cards were raised as the major security concerns in the park premises. Around 30% of women respondents raised concern about dense vegetation in different parts of the park. They did not feel very safe in and around these spaces. Presence of artificial lighting and visibility (being visible to others and to be able to see others) are considered as important factors by women and need of more signages by men to increase sense of security inside the park. Maintenance, police patrolling and cleanliness was given equal importance by both the genders to increase sense of security inside the park.

According to the survey around 18% of both genders have observed some kind of criminal activity inside the park and around 15% women themselves been victims of crime inside the park premises.

Fig.10: (A) Most secure spaces in the Park (B) Most unsafe zones in the park
(C) Security concerns inside the park (D) Factors/issues that will increase sense of security inside the park.

5.0 Discussions

The present study has brought attention to the various needs and substantial differences in gender perception of the design characteristics of urban green spaces. According to the survey results it can be inferred that there are differences in how men and women perceive spaces and they have different needs and expectations from urban green spaces.

According to the data, most of the women accessing the park, resided close by. They usually accompanied their kids, family or friends to visit the park. Men were more regular park visitors. More studies can be done to understand the reasons for less number of individual women accessing the park and why they are don't want or are not able to access the park frequently. Women found accessing the park as an opportunity for socializing with peer group or relaxing while the kids were busy in play areas. They preferred passive activities and found it as an escape from busy domestic duties. They preferred either quieter places like central green landscapes lawns or the rest areas next to the exercise equipments along the jogging trail or the open gym areas. While men were more involved in physical activities and utilized the jogging trail and exercise equipment more frequently. From the result of additional activities it can be inferred that that since women have more inclination for socializing and bonding with peer group, they preferred additional activity like community gardening. Men wanted an additional food kiosk with health and energy drinks.

Though 80% of respondents from both the genders stated park to be safe, but a deeper analysis highlights the difference in perception of safety by both men and women. Women feel more secure in areas which either has more number of users, like play areas or large meadow like green spaces where they can be seen by other users. Men felt secure in most spaces in the park, be that – the entry gates, periphery areas with dense vegetation or the central green spaces. Both the genders consider people who play cards/ drink alcohol and lack of CCTVs in parks as area of security concern. Women also considered washroom location, woodland area and peripheral area with dense vegetation as spaces of security concern because they feel threatened due to lack of clear visibility. Presence of Artificial lighting, police patrolling, maintenance and more signages were valued as important factors to reduce crime inside the park premises and for improving the safety perception by both the genders. The survey results show very less criminal activity in the study park but some women users have themselves been victim of crime. A further research on criminal activities reported inside the green spaces of a city can give clearer picture and help the designers and planners to make decisions on interventions need to reduce it.

5.1 Parameters from study

A qualitative analysis of the literature and a case study of district park in Delhi suggests certain parameters and factors that planners and policy makers need to consider when designing urban green spaces. These parameters are –

- i. The distance from green space affects the frequency of using it. The implication of distance on usage by women and weaker sections of the society is even more.
- ii. Different activities are preferred by different genders inside the park – recreation, passive/active activities, socializing, escaping from city life, clean air, aesthetics, psychological and physical health benefits etc.
- iii. Safety and vulnerability – women prefer spaces with more number of people and clear sight lines.
- iv. Different genders have different perceptions of green areas, which affect their inclination, health and the use of different spaces in the park.
- v. Public's trust and role in planning and management of urban greens.
- vi. User opinions, preferences, and attitudes towards urban green spaces.

Considering and incorporating these parameters will help bridge the gap between Delhi's green spaces and its users. To achieve this socially inclusive green space development in Delhi, it is important to ensure that programs, strategies and projects have a positive impact and strengthen gender equality as part of the development practices mentioned in the proposed MPD 2041. Architects must develop a new paradigm and rework on deeply rooted design conventions about how spaces are seen, used and designed. It has now become fundamental to discontinue overseeing human relations and their desires with the landscape. At present it has become essential to upgrade the current policies with recommendations for development features and design specifications for urban parks.

6.0 Conclusions

Urban green spaces are a critical part of cities as they are the areas for social interaction, and cultural expression. As per 2012 UN Habitat, Gender issue guide, the green spaces “embody the city's soul and image, as well as attract economic activities and creativity” (UN-Habitat, 2012). Gender is an imperative demographic variable affecting the design of urban green spaces.

Delhi is working towards making women feel safer in their local neighbourhoods and urban open spaces, by addressing gender safety as an important parameter in designing and planning of urban open spaces as part of their Master Plan and thus improving their quality of life. “Gender safety in urban open spaces” is the focus of proposed MPD 2041. More effort needs to be done in India to firstly understand the needs of various genders from urban green areas and then these needs have to be addressed through gender sensitive strategies and urban policy making. It is essential to collect and assess more data about Indian women's requirements and perception of urban green spaces.

7.0 Way Forward

The current planning and design practices basically ignore the gender-explicit experiences, perceptions, requirements, concerns and use of urban green spaces. Planners, Urban Designers and Landscape architects are engaged to plan for cities and new developments at various scales. They should explore and comprehend the distinctive challenges created by gender inequality. Without this sensitivity they will create more hurdles in gender sensitive design approach and decrease the effectiveness of planned mediations.

Once the government understands the importance of gender sensitive planning then more detailed studies/surveys have to be done to gather information for drafting gender sensitive policies. Data like current crime rates in green space, analysis of criminal activities experience by males and females and evaluation of the reason of crime in green spaces can help the designers and policy makers to understand the gender specific needs and expectations from urban parks. This would result in more gender inclusive strategies and policies that can be implemented in urban green spaces.

LITERATURE CITED

Cranz, G. (1980). Women in urban parks. *Signs*, 5(3), S79-S95. Retrieved from Spring, Chicago Journals.

Gupta, K., Roy, A., Luthra, K., Maithani, S., & Mahavir. (2016). GIS based analysis for assessing the accessibility at hierarchical levels of urban green spaces. *Urban Forestry and Urban Greening*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2016.06.005>

Huang, C., Huang, P., Wang, X., & Zhou, Z. (December 2017). Assessment and optimization of green space for urban transformation in resources-based city - a case study of Lengshuijiang city, China. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*. DOI: 10.1016/j.ufug.2017.12.016

İnce Güney, Y. (2014). Gender and urban space: An examination of a small Anatolian city. *ITU A|Z*, 11(2), 153-172.

Keshtkaran, R. (2019). Urban landscape: A review of key concepts and main purposes. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 8(2), 141-168. ISSN: 2186-8662.

Mayen, H. C., & Utomo, A. (2022). Barriers affecting women's access to urban green spaces during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Land*, 11, 560. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11040560>

Natu, A. (2008). Gendered use of landscapes: A case of community open spaces. *Landscape*, 22(winter). Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327509989>

Olta, B., Marco, G. C., & José, C. F. (2021). Gender differences in the perceptions of green spaces characteristics. *Social Science Quarterly*, 102, 2640–2648. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ssqu>

Pablo, N. H., Arielle, V., & Paz, C. (2021). Building safer public spaces: Exploring gender difference in the perception of safety in public space through urban design interventions. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 214, 104-180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2021.104180>

Palliwoda, J., & Priess, J. A. (2021). What do people value in urban green? Linking characteristics of urban green spaces to users' perceptions of nature benefits, disturbances, and disservices. *Ecology and Society*, 26(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12204-260128>

Paul, S., & Nagendra, H. (18 April 2017). Factors influencing perceptions and use of urban nature: Surveys of park visitors in Delhi. *Land*, 6, 27. doi:10.3390/land6020027

Phillips, A., Canters, F., & Khan, A. Z. (2022). Analyzing spatial inequalities in use and experience of urban green spaces. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 74.

Polko, P., & Kimic, K. (2022). Gender as a factor differentiating the perceptions of safety in urban parks. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2021.09.032>

Richardson, E. A., & Mitchell, R. (2010). Gender differences in relationships between urban green space and health in the United Kingdom. *Social Science & Medicine*, 71(3), 568-575.

Ridder, K. D., Adamec, V., Bañuelos, A., Brused, M., Bũrgerd, M., Damsgaard, O., ... Weber, C. (2004). An integrated methodology to assess the benefits of urban green space. *Science of the Total Environment*, 334-335, 489-497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2004.04.054>

Rozalija, C., Klemen, E., Marina, P., Špela, Ž., Dagmar, H., Nadja, K., & Michael, S. (13th May 2015). Typology of urban green spaces, ecosystem services provisioning services and demands. GREEN SURGE project (2013-2017), Report: D3.1, v.10.

Sanga, Å. O., Sanga, N., Hedblom, M., Sevelina, G., Knez, I., & Gunnarsson, B. (2020). Are path choices of people moving through urban green spaces explained by gender and age? Implications for planning and management. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2020.126628>

Sangwan, A., Saraswat, A., Kumar, N., Pipralia, S., & Kumar, A. (March 2022). Urban green spaces. In *Urban Green Spaces Prospects and Retrospects*. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.10285

The World Bank. (2020). *Handbook for gender-inclusive urban planning design*.

United Nations Human Settlements Programme (UN-Habitat). (2012). *Gender issue guide: Urban planning and design*.

Hindustan Times. (n.d.). Delhi one of the greenest cities, still falls way short of 33%. Hindustan Times. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/delhi/delhi-one-of-the-greenest-cities-still-falls-way-short-of-33/story-yKgVN2ew47SI3jB4QDudDO.html>

Times of India. (2022, July 5). Title of the article. Times of India. http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/articleshow/84441627.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst

Citizen Matters. (2022, December 27). How green is my city? Citizen Matters. <https://citizenmatters.in/how-green-is-my-city-1604>

India PL. (2023, July 27). Rohini District Park, Bhagawan Mahavir Marg, Sector 14, Rohini, Delhi. India PL. Retrieved Month Date, Year, from <https://indiapl.com>

Observer Research Foundation. (2021, December). The 'Green' in Delhi's Draft Master Plan: Weighed and Found Wanting. Observer Research Foundation. Issue no. 512.

United Nations. (n.d.). Sustainable Development Goals. United Nations. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. (n.d.). Urban Environmental Equity Program - Open Space. U.S. EPA Region 1. <https://www3.epa.gov/region1/eco/uep/openspace.html>

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.